

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Rhodium with Ethyl- α -isonitrosoacetoacetate

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A method is described for spectrophotometric determination of microgram quantities of Rh after extraction with ethyl- α -isonitrosoacetoacetate (HEINA) into methyl ethyl ketone. With 50 μg of Rh, the average of 10 determinations is 50.2 μg which varies between 47.7 μg and 52.7 μg at 95% confidence limit. The extracted species contains Rh and HEINA in the ratio of 1:2. It has been shown that HEINA can be employed for simultaneous determination of Rh, Ru and Pd by extractive spectrophotometric method.

ETHYL- α -isonitrosoacetoacetate has been used in the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of iron¹, palladium² and ruthenium³. In the present paper the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of rhodium with HEINA is reported and a method has been described for simultaneous determination of rhodium, ruthenium and palladium by extractive spectrophotometric method.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents: Absorbance measurements were taken on the PYE Unicam SP 500 and Carl-Zeiss VSU 2P spectrophotometers, using 1 cm silica cells. HEINA was prepared as reported earlier². A.R. grade chemicals and reagents were used. A stock solution of rhodium was prepared by dissolving 1 gm of rhodium chloride (J.M.) in 20 ml of 10 M HCl by heating on a water-bath and the solution was diluted to 100 ml with double distilled water. Rhodium was estimated as rhodium metal⁴. Dilute solutions of rhodium chloride were prepared by diluting appropriate quantities of the stock solution with double distilled water. Palladium and ruthenium solutions were prepared as described in the previous communications^{2,3}.

Procedure for extraction of rhodium: An aliquot of rhodium chloride solution was treated with 2 ml of 5% aqueous solution of HEINA and the pH was adjusted to the required value with hydrochloric acid and/or sodium hydroxide. The mixture solution was heated on a water-bath for 30 minutes, treated with an equal volume of 10 M LiCl solution and cooled to the room temperature ($\approx 25^\circ$). It was equilibrated for 2 minutes with 10 ml of methyl ethyl ketone. The two phases were separated and rhodium in each phase was estimated by the stannous chloride method⁵. The extraction coefficient for rhodium was calculated and separation factors were determined in the usual way.

Procedure for spectrophotometric determination of rhodium: To the rhodium solution containing 1 to 300 μg of rhodium, 2 ml of 5% aqueous solution of HEINA were added and pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.5 with sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (total volume 5 ml). It was heated for 30 minutes on a water-bath, treated with 5 ml of 10 M LiCl, cooled and equilibrated for 2 minutes twice with 5 ml portions of methyl ethyl ketone. The methyl ethyl ketone extracts were separated and collected in a 10-ml measuring flask. The volume of the solution was made up to the mark, if required, with methyl ethyl ketone and its absorbance was measured at 390 nm, using a reagent blank. The amount of rhodium was determined from the calibration curve, prepared by taking known amounts of rhodium and following the procedure described above.

Procedure for simultaneous determination of ruthenium, rhodium and palladium by extractive spectrophotometric method: A solution containing ruthenium (10-400 μg), rhodium (10-300 μg) and palladium (10-200 μg) was transferred into a 50-ml separatory funnel and was made 1 M with respect to acetic acid. Palladium was extracted into chloroform with HEINA and estimated spectrophotometrically as described elsewhere².

2 ml of 5% aqueous solution of HEINA were added to the aqueous phase containing ruthenium and rhodium. The pH was adjusted to 5.5 with sodium acetate solution. It was heated for 25 minutes on a water-bath, treated with an equal volume of 10 M LiCl solution, and cooled to the room temperature. Ruthenium was extracted by equilibrating the solution thrice with 8 ml portion of chloroform. The extracts were collected in a 25-ml measuring flask and made up to the mark with chloroform. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 470 nm, using a chloroform blank and the amount of ruthenium present was determined from the calibration curve prepared by taking known amounts of ruthenium and following the above procedure.

The aqueous phase containing rhodium was equilibrated twice with 5 ml portion of methyl ethyl ketone. The organic extracts were collected in a 10-ml measuring flask and the volume was made up to the mark with methyl ethyl ketone. The absorbance of the extract was measured at 390 nm and the amount of rhodium present was calculated with the help of a calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Extraction of rhodium : Present study reveals that methyl ethyl ketone extracts rhodium from an aqueous solution containing HEINA, provided the solution is heated to 90° for about 25 minutes before extraction. The extraction coefficient of rhodium increases with the increase in the pH of the aqueous solution from 0 to 5 and then it ($\epsilon=16$) remains constant in the pH range 5-6. Above pH 6 it decreases. The equilibration for 2 minutes is sufficient for reacting extraction equilibrium. The extraction coefficient value is enhanced, if the extraction is carried out in the presence of LiCl and it reaches maximum value ($\epsilon=42$) when the aqueous phase is 5 M with respect to LiCl. Salts such as AlCl₃, MgCl₂ etc. do not affect the extraction of rhodium. Of the solvents investigated, methyl ethyl ketone is found to be the most satisfactory solvent for the extraction of rhodium.

with carbon tetrachloride or chloroform, prior to the extraction of Rh into methyl ethyl ketone. Pt is separated by heating the solution at pH 1 with 2 ml of 5% aqueous HEINA for an hour and extracting into o-dichlorobenzene. Milligram amounts of gold are precipitated on heating the aqueous solution containing Rh and HEINA and so it can be easily removed by centrifugation. The loss of Rh due to the separation of Pd, Ru, Pt and Au is negligible.

Spectrophotometric determination of rhodium : The absorption spectrum of Rh-HEINA color in methyl ethyl ketone does not show any absorption peak in the visible range. The wavelength 390 nm is selected for absorbance measurements, because at this wavelength the absorption of the Rh-HEINA color is appreciable and the absorbance of the reagent is negligible (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Rh-HEINA complex (—○—○—) and HEINA (—●—●—) in methyl ethyl ketone. Rh=6 × 10⁻⁴M, HEINA=620 × 10⁻⁴M.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION FACTORS FOR DIFFERENT IONS IN THE EXTRACTION OF Rh-HEINA COMPLEX INTO METHYL ETHYL KETONE FROM 5M LiCl SOLUTION AT pH 5.5.

Separation factor (greater than)	Ions
	Rhodium taken —1 mg Volume of the aqueous phase—10 ml Volume of the organic phase—10 ml
10 ⁴	Zr, W ⁶⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , **Sn ²⁺
10 ⁵	Cs, Ca, Cd, Mn, Zn, *La, Ti ⁴⁺ , Mo ⁶⁺ , Re ⁷⁺ , *Cr ³⁺ , **Fe ²⁺ , **Sb ³⁺ , PO ₄ ³⁻
10 ⁴	K, Sc, Na, Ni, Ag, Ce ³⁺ , Au ³⁺ , Co ²⁺
10 ³	Ir ³⁺
10 ²	Pt ⁴⁺
10 ⁰	Ru ²⁺
10 ⁻¹	Pd

* In the presence of citrate.

** In the presence of tartrate.

Experimental data in Table 1 indicate that rhodium can be separated from a number of metals by extraction with HEINA into methyl ethyl ketone. Pd, Ru and Pt are coextracted with rhodium. The separation of rhodium from Pd can be achieved by extracting the latter from 1 M acetic acid solution with a solution of HEINA in chloroform. Ru is removed by extraction

At this wavelength Beer's law is obeyed over the range 1.0 to 30 µg of Rh per ml. The molar extinction coefficient of the extracted species is 5,500 l mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹, calculated on the basis of rhodium taken. The absorbance of the solution does not show any change for 48 hours. After this period, it decreases.

HEINA concentration corresponding to HEINA : Rh equal to 20 is sufficient for the extraction and color development of 100 µg of rhodium. However, in the presence of 10 mg of other ions, which interact with HEINA, it is necessary to use 100 mg of HEINA for the extraction of 100 µg of rhodium.

10 mg of the ions U^{6+} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Be^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Mo^{6+} , W^{6+} , Th^{4+} , Ba^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Ag^+ , Te^{6+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , chloride, bromide, iodide, chlorate, bromate, sulphite, sulphate, persulphate, phosphate, pyrophosphate, nitrate, citrate, tartrate, oxalate and EDTA, 5 mg of Os^{4+} and 1 mg of each of Au^{3+} , Se^{4+} and Se^{6+} do not interfere in the spectrophotometric estimation of Rh. The interference by Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Sn^{2+} and Sb^{5+} can be removed by using tartrate as a masking agent. Pd, Ru and Pt are separated by the procedures described before, prior to the estimation of Rh. With 100 μg of Rh, 20 μg of each of Ir and Co can be tolerated. The interference by iodate can be removed by adding KI and heating the solution on a water-bath. Cyanide is removed by heating with formaldehyde.

The precision and accuracy of the method were determined by analysing 10 solutions containing known amounts of rhodium. With 50 μg of rhodium in 10 ml solution, the average of 10 determinations is 50.2 μg which varies between 47.7 μg and 52.7 μg at 95% confidence limit. The absorbance of the solution containing 1 μg per ml of Rh is 0.05.

Simultaneous determination of ruthenium, rhodium and palladium: The results in Table 2 suggest that HEINA can be successfully employed for simultaneous determination of Rh, Ru and Pd by extractive spectrophotometric method.

TABLE 2—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF RUTHENIUM, RHODIUM AND PALLADIUM BY EXTRACTIVE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD.

Sl. No.	Amount of metal taken (μg)			Amount of metal found after separation (μg)		
	Ru	Rh	Pd	Ru	Rh	Pd
1.	10.0	—	10.0	10.0	—	10.0
2.	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0
3.	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	10.0	99
4.	100	10.0	100	99	10.0	99
5.	100	100	100	100	101	100
6.	400	100	10.0	397	100	10.0
7.	400	300	10.0	397	298	10.0
8.	400	300	200	397	298	200

Nature of the extracted rhodium species: Curves obtained by Job's continuous variation method (Fig. 2) show a sharp maxima at 0.34 mole fraction of rhodium, indicating that the colored complex is formed by the reaction of Rh and HEINA in the ratio of 1:2. The straight line graph in the mole ratio method (Fig. 3) reveals a sharp break at the point corresponding to HEINA: Rh equal to 2:1, which is in agreement with the results of the Job's continuous variation method.

Fig. 2. Job's continuous variation method. Concentration of Rh and HEINA = $2.5 \times 10^{-8} M$, $-\Delta-\Delta-$ at 340 nm, $-\bullet-\bullet-$ at 390 nm and $-\circ-\circ-$ at 410 nm.

Fig. 3. Mole ratio method. $-\bullet-\bullet-$ at 340 nm and $-\circ-\circ-$ at 390 nm.

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